

The Effect of Ion-pairing on the Solvolytic Aquation of Chloropentaammine-cobalt(III) Ion in the Presence of Maleate and Phthalate Anions

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The rate of solvolytic aquation of chloropentaammine cobalt(III) ion has been measured in aqueous medium in the presence of maleate and phthalate anions at 40°, 45° and 50°. The rate accelerating influence of maleate and phthalate has been attributed to more labile ion-pairs and the rate and association constants of the ion-pairs have been calculated. Product analysis has been carried out to examine the participation of the associating anions in the act of substitution. Activation parameters of the aquation reaction of the ion-pairs and of the other reaction path-ways have been evaluated. Enthalpy, entropy and free energy changes of the association equilibria have also been evaluated.

A CONSIDERABLE body of information is available pertaining to the acid hydrolysis reaction of octahedral amino complexes of cobalt(III) and chromium(III). It has been shown by Monk *et al*^{9,11,12}, that the rate of aquation of halopentaammine complexes of cobalt(III) and chromium(III) is significantly accelerated in the presence of certain bivalent anions. The rate accelerating influence has been ascribed to the formation of more labile ion-pairs between the complex cation and the added anions. However, the mechanistic path-ways for the aquation of the ion-pairs have not been unequivocally elucidated. In a previous communication¹³, we have reported on the rate accelerating effect of sulphate ion on the aquation kinetics of chloropentaammine-cobalt(III) complex. The present communication deals with the rate accelerating influence of maleate and phthalate anions on the acid hydrolysis reaction of chloropentaammine cobalt(III) ion.

Experimental

Preparation of the Complexes. Chloropentaammine-cobalt(III) perchlorate, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$, was prepared and purified as suggested by Chan and co-workers¹⁴. The chloride and cobalt content of the complex were estimated to check the purity of the sample. (Found: Co, 15.35; Cl, 9.3 per cent. Calc. for $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$: Co, 15.57, Cl 9.4 per cent).

The measured molar absorptivity ($\text{cm}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$) of 50.5 at 532 nm is in excellent agreement with the value of 50.5 reported in the literature¹⁵.

Aquopentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorate, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}](\text{ClO}_4)_3$, was prepared and purified by the reported method¹⁶. The measured molar absorptivity of $\epsilon_{492} = 47.8$ is in fair agreement with the values $\epsilon_{492} = 47.7^{15}$ and $\epsilon_{491} = 47.3^{16}$ reported previously.

Phthalato-pentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorate, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{O}_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and maleato-pentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorate ($\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{C}_4\text{H}_3\text{O}_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$) were prepared and purified as described in literature^{17,18}. The analytical data in respect of cobalt contents and molar absorptivities are given below: (Found: Co, 11.5 per cent. Calc. for $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{O}_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$: Co, 11.61 per cent). (Found: Co, 13.01 per cent. Calc. for $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{C}_4\text{H}_3\text{O}_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$: Co, 12.87 per cent).

The measured molar absorptivity of 80 at 500 nm for the phthalato-pentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorate is in good agreement with the reported¹⁹ value of 80 at 502-503 nm. The measured molar absorptivity of $\epsilon_{500} = 73$ for the maleato-pentaamminecobalt(III)-perchlorate is in conformity with the range of values suggested for carboxylato-pentaamminecobalt(III) complexes¹⁹.

The sodium salts of the acids were prepared by mixing together requisite amounts of sodium hydroxide and the respective acids of known concentration. Reagent grade sodium perchlorate was used for adjusting ionic strength. Double distilled water was used for preparing all solutions.

Kinetic Experiments

(i) *Acid Hydrolysis of the complex*: For the measurement of rate constants, reaction mixtures were prepared by mixing requisite volumes of all reagent solutions excepting the complex in the reaction vessel and thermostatted at the temperature of the experiment. After attainment of thermal equilibrium, a weighed amount of the complex was quickly transferred into the reaction vessel. The solid dissolved rapidly on shaking. Distilled water, equilibrated at the same temperature was used to make up the volume 5 ml. aliquots were withdrawn at appropriate time intervals and quenched in an ice-cold acetone-water mixture²⁰, acidified with a few drops of concentrated nitric acid. The chloride ion released by aquation was titrated potentiometrically with standard silver nitrate solution.

(ii) *Entry of carboxylate anions*. With a view to examine the formation of the respective carboxylato-pentaamminecobalt(III) complexes by entry of the added dicarboxylate anions, reaction mixtures identical with the above were simultaneously prepared and thermostatted at the desired temperature. Aliquots were withdrawn from the reaction vessel at known intervals into well-stoppered test-tubes (pyrex) and quenched in ice-bath. The optical densities of the solutions were recorded at appropriate wave lengths on a Beckmann DU-2 spectrophotometer. Matched 1 cm silica cells were used for such measurements, double distilled water being used as the 100 per cent transmission standard.

Results

The pseudo-unimolecular rate constants for the release of chloride ion from the complex were derived from the plots of $\log(v_\infty - v_t)$ vs. time 't' where 'v_t' is the volume of silver nitrate consumed after time interval of 't', 'v_∞' being the volume required for complete reaction. 'v_∞' was invariably computed from the weight of the complex taken. The results obtained are recorded in Table 1.

The aquation rate constants of the free complex ion have been determined at 40°, 45° and 50°. The interaction of the free complex ion with the added maleate and phthalate anions would be expected to result in the formation of outer-sphere complexes or ion-pairs of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}^{+2}, \text{L}^{-2}]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}^{+2}, \text{HL}^-]$, where L⁻² and HL⁻ stand for the bivalent and univalent anions respectively. The observed rate constant for the aquation of the complex in the presence of the added anions would, therefore, be a composite term consisting of the rate constant of the free complex ion and the rate and equilibrium constants of the ion-pairs as suggested by Wyatt and Davies²¹. Assuming that the free complex ion and the ion-pair formed by the free-ion with univalent anions, CpHL⁺ react at the same rate^{7,8,9}, the rate law for the aquation reaction at constant ionic strength will be represented by

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-dc}{dt} = k_{obs} \times c = k_1[\text{Cp}^{+2}] + k_{tp}[\text{CpL}] \quad (1)$$

TABLE I. ACID HYDROLYSIS OF $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION IN THE PRESENCE OF MALEATE (MALE⁻²) AND PHTHALATE (PH⁻²) ANIONS

Concentration of the complex = $5 \times 10^{-3} M$.			Ionic strength = 0.3M					
$[\text{HClO}_4]$ $\times 10^3 M$	$[\text{HL}^-]$ $\times 10^3 M$	$[\text{L}^{-2}]$ $\times 10^3 M$	$k_{obs} \times 10^5 / \text{sec}^*$			$k_{tp} \times 10^5 / \text{sec}$		
			40°	45°	50°	40°	45°	50°
10	—	—	1.02	1.87	3.36	—	—	—
—	5(NaHMale)	5(Na ₂ Male)	1.20	2.14	3.66	2.78	4.73	7.09
—	10(NaHMale)	10(Na ₂ Male)	1.35	2.35	3.91	2.79	4.72	7.08
—	20(NaHMale)	20(Na ₂ Male)	1.57	2.67	4.33	2.77	4.74	7.10
—	30(NaHMale)	30(Na ₂ Male)	1.72	2.97	—	2.78	4.73	—
—	50(NaHMale)	50(Na ₂ Male)	1.94	—	—	2.78 (24)	— (21)	— (18)
—	5(NaHPh)	5(Na ₂ Ph)	1.21	2.19	3.73	2.93	5.45	8.14
—	10(NaHPh)	10(Na ₂ Ph)	1.38	2.46	4.04	2.97	5.45	8.08
—	20(NaHPh)	20(Na ₂ Ph)	1.62	2.89	4.57	2.95	5.46	8.12
—	30(NaHPh)	30(Na ₂ Ph)	1.80	—	—	2.94 (26.9)	— (23.6)	— (20.0)

*The observed rate constants are accurate upto ±1 per cent. The K_{tp} values are given in the parantheses at the end of the system under the k_{tp} readings.

$k_3^0(i_p)$ was evaluated spectrophotometrically in the same manner as reported previously¹³. It has been assumed that the anation rate constants k_2 ($=k_2(i_p) \times K_{aq}$) for the maleate and phthalate systems are of the same order of magnitude as that for sulphate system²⁴, since such data for maleate and phthalate are not available in literature. Sulphate ion and the carboxylate dianions being of the same charge type, this assumption appears to be reasonable since it is known that the rate constants for the anation of $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}^{+3}$ by univalent anions^{1(a)} are of the same order of magnitude ($\sim 2 \times 10^{-6}$ at 25° , $\mu = 0.5$).

D_t , the optical density of a solution, containing $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}^{+2}$ and L^{-2} ion at 510 nm at any time 't' may be expressed as¹³

$$D_t = E_1 A_0 e^{-k_{obs}t} + \frac{E_2 A_0 k_{obs}}{k_2 - k_{obs}} (e^{-k_{obs}t} - e^{-k_2t}) + E_3 \left[\frac{A_0 k_{obs} e^{-k_2t}}{k_2 - k_{obs}} - \frac{k_2 A_0 e^{-k_{obs}t}}{k_2 - k_{obs}} - \frac{k_3(i_p) A_0 e^{-k_{obs}t}}{k_{obs}} + \frac{A_0 k_3(i_p)}{k_{obs}} + A_0 \right] \quad \dots (13)$$

E_1, E_2 and E_3 are the molar absorptivities of the chloro, aquo and carboxylato-pentaammine cobalt(III) complexes respectively at a path length of 1 cm. A_0 refers to the concentration of $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}^{+2}$ at zero time. $k_3(i_p)$ was calculated by using eqn. (13) with the help of an one parameter search programme (parameter being $k_3(i_p)$) as already described¹³.

$k_3^0(i_p)$ was calculated from the equation

$$k_3(i_p) = \frac{k_3^0(i_p) K_{ip} [L^{-2}]}{1 + K_{ip} [L^{-2}]_f} \quad \dots (14)$$

The $k_{ip}, k_2, k_3(i_p)$ and $k_3^0(i_p)$ values have been recorded in Table 2.

Computation of activation and thermodynamic parameters. The activation parameters, $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ for the reaction paths k_1, k_{ip} and $k_3^0(i_p)$ and the thermodynamic parameters for the ion-association equilibria involving $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}^{+2}$ ion and maleate and phthalate anions were calculated by the procedures described previously¹³. The data have been collected in Table 3.

TABLE 2. RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE $k_{ip}, k_2, k_3(i_p)$ AND $k_3^0(i_p)$ PATHS OF REACTION

System	$[L^{-2}] \times 10^2 M$	Path-way	Temp.			
			40°	45°	50°	
Maleate		$k_{ip} \times 10^6/\text{sec}$	2.78	4.73	7.09	
		$k_2 \times 10^4/\text{sec}$	1.12	2.10	3.85	
	1.00	$k_3(i_p) \times 10^6/\text{sec}$	—	—	1.37 ± 0.09	
	2.00		0.23 ± 0.07	0.93 ± 0.09	1.74 ± 0.09	
	4.00		0.45 ± 0.07	1.20 ± 0.12	2.35 ± 0.09	
	6.00		0.51 ± 0.08	1.59 ± 0.10	—	
	10.00		0.83 ± 0.08	—	—	
			$k_3^0(i_p) \times 10^6/\text{sec}$	1.03 ± 0.10	1.88 ± 0.04	3.07 ± 0.15
			$k_{ip} \times 10^6/\text{sec}$	2.94	5.45	8.11
			$k_2 \times 10^4/\text{sec}$	1.12	2.10	3.85
Phthalate		$k_3(i_p) \times 10^6/\text{sec}$	—	—	—	
	1.00		—	0.50 ± 0.07	1.78 ± 0.08	
	2.00		0.32 ± 0.06	0.86 ± 0.06	2.47 ± 0.08	
	4.00		0.49 ± 0.06	1.10 ± 0.06	3.30 ± 0.09	
	6.00		0.68 ± 0.06	—	—	
		$k_3^0(i_p) \times 10^6/\text{sec}$	1.05 ± 0.08	1.95 ± 0.10	3.57 ± 0.10	

TABLE 3. ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE k_1 , k_{ip} AND $k_3^0(i_p)$ PATHS OF REACTION AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ION-ASSOCIATION PROCESS

System	k_1 path			k_{ip} path			$k_3^0(i_p)$ path			Ion-association process		
	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ (k. cal/ mole)	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ (k. cal/ mole at 40°)	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ (k. cal/ mole)	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ (k. cal/ mole at 40°)	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ (k. cal/ mole)	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ (k. cal/ mole at 40°)	ΔH (k. cal/ mole)	ΔS e.u.	ΔG (k. cal/ 40°)
Free-ion	23.04 ± 0.2	-6.7 ± 0.6	25.5	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Maleate	—	—	—	18.05 ± 0.07	-21.8 ± 0.2	24.9 ± 0.02	22.4 ± 0.8	-14.4 ± 2.5	26.95 ± 0.01	-6.0	-12.6	-2.0
Phthalate	—	—	—	17.2 ± 0.1	-24.1 ± 0.4	24.8 ± 0.01	22.10 ± 0.9	-15.4 ± 2.9	26.92 ± 0.02	-6.4	-13.9	-2.1

Discussion

In the presence of maleate and phthalate ions a significant rate acceleration of the acid hydrolysis of the chloropentaammine cobalt(III) complex results. The enhancement of the rate in the presence of added anions is ascribed to the formation of more reactive ion-pairs. The ratios of the ion-pair rate constants to the free ion rate constant at 40°, 45° and 50° for the maleate and phthalate ion-pairs are found to be 2.72, 2.52 and 2.11; 2.90, 2.90 and 2.41 respectively. The decrease of this ratio with increase in temperature can be attributed to the lower free energy of activation of the ion-pairs compared to that of the free ion. The k_{ip}/k_1 ratios for the oxalate²⁵, sulphate¹³, malonate, succinate²⁵, maleate and phthalate²³ systems at 40° are found to be 1.97, 2.20, 2.25, 2.28, 2.72 and 2.90 respectively, the association constants of the corresponding ion-pairs being 33.4, 32.5, 32.2, 28.4, 24.0 and 26.9 at the same temperature. From the above results it is obvious that the thermodynamic stability of the ion-pairs do not appear to govern their reactivity.

The greater reactivity of the ion-pairs may be visualised to be predominantly due to an electrostatic effect. Ion-pair formation would result in the decrease of the overall charge of the complex and thereby favour the expulsion of the chloride ion by a dissociative mechanism. The transition state may, therefore, be visualised to involve considerable degree of charge separation and hence loss of activation entropy. The low negative entropies of activation for the ion-pairs (Table 3) is indicative of a dissociative mechanism for the aquation of the ion-pairs with a square-pyramidal transition state in accordance with Tobe's observation²⁶.

A linear free energy treatment²⁷ involving plots of $\log k_{ip}$ (k_{ip} = ion-pair rate constant) vs. pK_{ip} (K_{ip} = ion-pair association constant) gave reasonably good straight lines with unit slopes at 40°, 45° and 50°. The data for sulphate¹³ and oxalate, malonate and succinate²⁵ also fall on these plots. The unit slopes of these plots, according to Langford²⁸ also point to a dissociative process for the reaction.

The amounts of carboxylato-pentaammine complexes formed via $k_2(i_p)$ and $k_3^0(i_p)$ path-ways were

found out from the product analysis experiment. The optical density vs. time plots²⁹ invariably passed through a minimum which became shallower with increase in temperature and anion concentration. The molar absorptivities of maleato-, phthalato-, chloro- and aquo-pentaammine cobalt(III) complexes at 510 nm are 74, 82, 45 and 47 respectively. It is, therefore, reasonable to believe that the formation of the carboxylato-pentaammine cobalt(III) predominantly proceeds through the anation of the aquo-carboxylate ion-pairs (k_2 path). The agreement between the experimental optical density and the optical density calculated using the scheme I was found to be excellent which stands in support of this view.

From the results in Tables 1 and 2 it is found that about 10 percent in the maximum of chloride is released from the chloropentaammine cobalt(III) complex through $k_3^0(i_p)$ path, compared to the k_1 , k_{ip} and $k_2^0(i_p)$ path-ways taken together. The rate constants for the formation of maleato- and phthalato-pentaammine cobalt(III) complexes through $k_3^0(i_p)$ path are calculated to be $1.62 \times 10^{-7}/\text{sec}$ and $1.69 \times 10^{-7}/\text{sec}$ respectively at 25°. The rate constants for the formation of such complexes by anation of the corresponding aquo-carboxylate ion-pairs are assumed to be the same as in case of sulphate, that is $1.3 \times 10^{-6}/\text{sec}$ at 25°. From these values, it is evident that only 12.5 per cent of maleato and 13 per cent of phthalato pentaammine cobalt(III) complexes are formed by the $k_3^0(i_p)$ path compared to the $k_2(i_p)$ path. Hence it is reasonable to assume that the chloride release takes place predominantly through the formation of aquo complex.

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